

RESULTS OF HYDRO AND GAS HYDRODYNAMIC STUDIES OF WELLS AND FORMATIONS FOR DUAL COMPLETION OF WELLS

Deryaev A.

*Candidate of Technical Sciences, Senior Researcher,
Scientific Research Institute of Natural Gas
of the State Concern „Turkmengas”,
Ashgabat, Turkmenistan*

Abstract

The article presents the results of complex field studies of oil wells and formations of the Altygyi field in order to establish gas dynamic parameters, as well as to study their gas condensate characteristics. The main attention in the study of wells and reservoirs was paid to a more accurate determination of the initial value of reservoir pressure, temperature, bottom-hole pressure, oil density and pressure recovery curve, which were carried out under various operating modes of wells. Based on the results of the conducted research, the justification for the allocation of operational facilities, their drilling systems, taking into account the need for dual completion (DC) in wells, was carried out.

Keywords: flow rate, pressure gauge, bottom-hole zone, filtration mode, hydroconductivity, separator, oil.

The determination of the initial indicators of wells and formations at the Altygyi deposit was achieved using the method of steady-state sampling, which, even under steady-state filtration regimes in the bottom-hole zone of the formation, were carried out in order to establish the gas-dynamic parameters of the formation and wells, to study their gas-condensate characteristics.

The filtration mode was changed by selecting the diameter of the fitting at the wellhead.

The duration of operation in oil and gas wells for at least 24 hours and for gas condensate wells in each mode was from 5 to 24 hours. The measurement on each mode began after the full stabilization of the wellhead pressures of P_{buf} and P_{annul} .

The measurement of reservoir and bottom-hole pressures and the recording of the pressure recovery curve were carried out with deep pressure gauges of the MGN2-800kg/cm² type and MSU-1-100-160 and in some places with electronic geophysical devices "Granite" and "Sakmar".

The necessary indicators for calculating the determination of the daily gas flow rate were carried out using a separator of the PBS-350/64 type with a measuring diaphragm with a diameter of 50 mm.

Measurements of the daily gas flow rate were carried out using a complex field installation equipped with a separator of the "Demag" type and flow meters of the DSP-0.063 and DPS-1.6 types.

The parameters for determining the gas flow rate were calculated using 4- or 2-inch diaphragm meters of

critical gas flow (DICT) [1].

Wellhead pressures (P_{buf} and P_{annul}) were recorded with model pressure gauges of the MO type at 250, 400 and 600 kgf/cm², accuracy class ± 1 , $\pm 0.6\%$ and $\pm 0.4\%$.

Bottom-hole and reservoir temperatures are determined by thermometers with mercury columns of the TP-7 type.

In some facilities, it was not possible to close the well to the reservoir pressure value due to technical reasons. In these circumstances, the reservoir pressure was determined by the experimental method [2].

Application of the method under steady-state filtration conditions of products in the bottom-hole zone of the formation for trial operation (with a change in mode), complex hydrodynamic studies were carried out in 17 objects, 16 wells, in an amount of 22 times. Only on 6 wells (№№12, 19, 107, 108, 111 and 112), measurements of the daily flow rate were carried out, and in 4 wells (№№ 7, 21, 105 and 107), a one-time measurement of reservoir and bottom-hole pressure was carried out. At oil well sites № 2 and № 7, the study was carried out by the method of normalizing the fluid flow – pressure recovery curve (PRC). As a result of processing the obtained materials, the coefficient of hydroconductivity and permeability of the formation was calculated by the Horner method. The obtained results of the development, measurements and their definition are given in the table. Graphs of the pressure recovery curve are shown in Figures 1 and 2.

Table.

The results of hydrodynamic studies at the wells of the Altyguyi field

Well num-ber	Horizon	Perforation interval (m)	Fitting diameter (m)	Coefficient			Note	
				Capacity (kg/cm ²)	Hydroconductivity (sP)	Permeability (mD)		
Research in order								
1(I)	NK ₉	3670-3680	5	-	-	-		
			6	-	-	-		
			8	-	-	-		
			-	0,1807	4,4	14,52		
			Repeated research					
			6	-	-	-		
			5	-	-	-		
			4,8	-	-	-		
			5,6	-	-	-		
			6,4	0,264	6,43	21,2		
2(I)	NK ₉	3608-3618	4	-	-	-		
			5	-	-	-		
			6	0,9043	10.1 on PRC	34,34 on PRC		
3(I)	NK ₉	3732-3738	4	-	-	-		
			5	-	-	-		
			6	0,171	4,2	23,1		
4	NK ₉	3728-3740	4,8	-	-	-		
			5,6	-	-	-		
			6,4	1,1107	27,1	74,53		
7(II)	NK ₉	3746-3750	4	-	-	-		
			4,8	-	-	-		
			3,1	0,8493	22,03 on PRC	93,4 on PRC		
10(I)	NK ₉	3653-3662	6,3	-	-	-		
			8,0	-	-	-		
			4,8	0,4914	12,00	44,0		
106(I)	NK ₉	3783-3792	4	-	-	-		
			5	-	-	-		
			6	1,3552	33,0	-		

Fig. 1. Graph of the curve of recovery of bottom-hole pressure to reservoir pressure, during the study of production well № 2 of the Altyguyi field

Fig. 2. Graph of the curve of recovery of bottom-hole pressure to reservoir pressure, during the study of the II-th object of the exploration well № 7 of the Altyguyi field

The specific gravity of Altyguyi oil in comparison with the oil of other fields in the Southwestern part of Turkmenistan is very heavy (0.910 g/cm^3) and has a lot of paraffin in its composition. In the process of oil extraction, the paraffin contained in the product freezes due to a decrease in temperature at a depth of 800-1000 meters. In this regard, the freezing of paraffin leads to a decrease in the inner diameter of the tubing, an increase in downhole pressure and a decrease in daily oil production [3]. This phenomenon has the opposite effect on determining the productivity coefficient of the well and the exact calculation of some reservoir indicators.

Before conducting hydro and gas dynamic studies, it is recommended to clean the inner walls of the tubing from the layers of paraffin.

Taking into account the above, the proposed values of the initial reservoir pressure and temperature of the NK₉ oil horizon are assumed to be the values of the accurately performed measurements of the II-th object of well № 7 - 643 kgf/cm^3 and 87°C .

References

1. Муравьев В.М. Эксплуатация нефтяных и газовых скважин. – М.: Недра 1978. – с.495.
2. Нефтепромысловое оборудование. Справочник. / под редакцией Е.И.Бухаленко – М: Недра. 1990.
3. Игнатенко Ю.К., Н.Р. Акопян и др. Временная инструкция по удалению жидкости из газовых и газоконденсатных скважин с помощью пенообразующих веществ. Ставрополь. 1977. с.12-15.